

BEING RED-TAGGED ACTIVISTS: THE CASE OF THREE SOUTH COTABATEÑOS

Erica P. Immapi, Sjavee Krystel A. Cabel, Kristyl Jane C. Cabisado,
Jun Y. Badie, Ph.D

Notre Dame of Marbel University, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15158998>

ABSTRACT

This study delved into the experiences of being red-tagged activists of the three South Cotabateños. The study utilized a single – holistic case study which allowed the researchers to look closely at the participants’ experiences of being red-tagged activists, their challenges and coping strategies from their involvement in activism. The researchers conducted a one-on-one interview. The results indicated that the red-tagged activists faced challenges along the way and coping strategies in order for them to survive from the label. Despite the challenges, the red-tagged activists exhibited resilience by adopting proactive bold strategies to mitigate the labeling they experience. However, they have experienced a dangerous phenomenon that they have to deal with, especially when there are circumstances that are not favorable for them. Moreover, the experience of being red-tagged highlights a system that aims to suppress dissent and silence those who challenge it, yet it also serves as a powerful call to action. To lessen the prevalence of red-tagging, it is essential for the government to implement reforms that safeguard human rights, encourage open dialogue, and create a more inclusive environment for dissenting voices. This includes strengthening laws that prevent discrimination, harassment, and violence against those labeled as communist or terrorist threats.

Keywords: *Red-tagged activists, experiences, challenges, coping strategies, resilience, single-holistic case study, red-tagging, activists, challenges, coping strategies*

INTRODUCTION

During the Cold War, it was used in the Red Scare to equate communism with terrorism. In the 1930s, socialist systems emerged in the global south, and red-tagging became a tool to criminalize activism. Today, activists exercising their democratic rights are often blacklisted, labeled as enemies of the state, and even murdered for opposing government corruption (Lorenzana, 2021). Thongyoojaroen (2023) highlighted that in the Philippines, critics of the government—journalists, activists, and community leaders—are often accused of ties to communist groups like the NPA. She added that since 2016, red-tagging under Duterte’s administration has led to 801 political prisoners and 442 extrajudicial killings, targeting those labeled as communists.

Human Rights Watch (2024) has stated that the Philippines have become one of the most dangerous countries in Asia for environmental activists and land defenders because of the harassment and attacks on Indigenous peoples. Philippine authorities present individuals such as leftists, political activists, journalists, teachers, clergy, Indigenous leaders, youth activists, and politicians who were labeled as red-tagged because they support the communist New People’s Army (Lau, 2024).

Last May 8, 2024, the Supreme Court of the Philippines issued a major ruling that red-tagging is a threat to a people’s civil rights which is the right to life, liberty, and security (Human Rights Watch, 2024). The Supreme Court of the Philippines further discussed that Mr. Deduro, an activist residing in Iloilo, has been red-tagged as he was once followed by an unknown individual. Moreover, he also experienced that his pictures were lingering in the city and labeled as members of the Communist Party of the Philippines-New People’s Army (CPP-NPA). The Regional Trial Court has dismissed his petition because according to RTC, his proof of being red-tagged is insufficient to prove his threat to life, liberty and security. However, the Supreme Court has granted Mr. Deduro a prima facie warranting him the issuance of writ of amparo (Pio, 2024).

From the literature the researchers have gathered, it explains that the Philippines is a country where red-tagging is a dominant issue among other countries. All literature that can be seen when looking into the topic, the Philippines is leading in searching websites. However, the researchers have identified that there is a literature gap in this study. All throughout the Philippines, red-tagged activists in South Cotabato are one of those who were silenced and attacked by multiple death threats, surveillance, and many harmful executions without being recognized and protected by the government. Thus, this study aimed to shed light on the experiences of activists targeted with this harmful practice which is red-tagging. It described the firsthand accounts of three individuals in South Cotabato, detailing the methods used for red-tagging, the impact on their personal lives and activism, and the coping strategies they have developed. This in-depth exploration is interwoven with understanding the broader context of red-tagging in the province. The researchers described the experiences and the challenges faced by the participants. Ultimately, this research aspires to contribute valuable knowledge to the fight against red-tagging and its negative effects on activists on the democracy of the Philippines.

Red-tagging in the Philippines

Similar to McCarthyism in the 1950, red-tagging is done here in the Philippines; it is a practice of labeling individuals or groups as communist fronts, communist-terrorists, or communist sympathizers (Advox, 2023).

According to Gavilan (2021), independent observers have documented the harmful practice of red-tagging, which involves falsely accusing individuals and groups of being communists. Red-tagging refers to organizations or individuals with connections to anti-government communist groups, often without documentation. According to Human Rights Watch, journalists and activists who opposed the government were harassed in court (Aquino, 2023).

President Duterte and his administration used this tactic to suppress criticism, targeting various sectors including journalists, doctors, activists, and students, accusing them of being terrorists or communist without any evidence. Journalists, professors, and students could be subject to imprisonment and physical assault (Olmi, 2021).

Palma, Morada, Hubilla, and Bagasala are members of leftist organizations who had been red-tagged and identified by the government as the Communist Party of the Philippines legal fronts. In January 2018, President Duterte condemned these groups, and they claimed increased attacks from unidentified individuals, including murders (Amnesty International, 2021).

Red-tagging undermines press freedom by labeling civil society and activist groups as communist or terrorist, making them dangerous to interview or cover. According to De Santos, red-tagging also undermines press freedom by putting red-tagged journalists at risk of intimidation and attacks offline in addition to online harassment, affecting the validity of issues and the credibility of journalists reporting on them (Crispin, 2022).

The Committee to Protect Journalists (CPJ) alleged that red-tagging was a government policy after the Duterte administration established the National Task Force to End Local Communist Armed Conflict (NTF-ELCAC) in 2018. It uses social media to connect journalists, activists, lawyers, and civil society organizations with the communist insurrection, which the task force views as a key threat to achieving inclusive and sustainable peace (Santisas, 2022). Three Senate hearings discussed the practice of red-tagging where activists and critics are labeled as communist insurgents. Military leaders and NTF-ELCAC supporters defended their actions, citing similarities between underground and legal movements. The practice poses a significant risk, but witnesses' veracity is questionable (Beltran, 2020).

Government officials' red-tagging campaigns restrict freedom by accusing people of communist insurgency ties. Resolution should demand an end to red-tagging, intimidation of activists, and arrests.

Red-tagging as a Threat to Life of Activists

Red-tagging in the Philippines, where activists and journalists are falsely labeled as communists or terrorists has led to numerous arrests and killings, Human Rights report

that being red-tagged, poses a significant threat to civil society, leading to arrests and violence (CIVICUS, 2023). In the Philippines, authorities use red-baiting to falsely accuse critics of being communists or terrorists, thereby stifling activists, human rights defenders, and peaceful organizations from facing human rights abuses (Pingel, 2014). The Philippines, despite its constitution guaranteeing press freedom, is one of the world's riskiest locations for journalists, facing physical attacks, threats, smear campaigns, red-tagging, and distributed denial of service attacks (Freedom House, 2023). The Philippines faces red-tagging, where journalists reporting on human rights violations are labeled as terrorists or communists, with Bulatlat being a constant target, causing severe consequences. Ellao emphasizes the impact of being red-tagged, it is like receiving a death threat (Kumar, 2023).

Beverly Longid, national convener of Katribu, is an outspoken campaigner with extensive experience as an environmental defender. She had received anonymous death threats through social media and direct messages. She was also called communist sympathizer. According to her, many have been arrested and killed, and some have disappeared because they experienced being red-tagged (Human Rights Watch, 2023).

Red-tagging in the Philippines has increased under Duterte's administration due to his harsh drug war and anti-terrorism legislation, resulting in hundreds of deaths, including lawyers, journalists, and activists. According to Conde (2023) of Human Rights Watch, many of the red-tagged activist groups refrained from taking part in the violent battle despite having ideological ties to communists.

The Commission on Human Rights views left-leaning political groups as front organizations for armed groups whose aim is to destroy democracy and as enemies of the State, making them a legitimate target. Remulla discussed red-tagging at the UN Human Rights Committee, describing it as a term used to criticize civil society organizations for their involvement in criminal acts (Remulla, 2022).

Red tagging, a practice originating from the 1972 civil conflict between the Philippine state and the Communist Party, indicates political rivals' connections to the New People's Army. The fight against Muslim separatists in the country's south presents two fronts on which the nation is engaged in a civil war. When a political rival is red-tagged, it indicates that they have been connected to the Communist Party's military wing, the New People's Army, and when someone is red-tagged, false accusations are filed against them out of nowhere or they are taken into custody or perhaps killed (Bright, 2023).

Philippine officials red-tagging of indigenous leaders and activists poses a threat to their communities. According to Phil Robertson, deputy Asia director at Human Rights Watch, indigenous communities have the right to peacefully express their views and protect their land and cultural heritage without fear of violence (Human Rights Watch, 2024).

Following the breakdown of peace talks between the government and the Communist Party of the Philippines (CPP) in 2017, former President Rodrigo Duterte's administration resumed red-tagging. This tactic has resulted in harassment, threats, attacks, and

murders of human rights defenders, political activists, attorneys, trade unionists, and other groups thought to be associated with the left (Amnesty Philippines, 2023).

Under the Duterte's administration, several church workers in the Philippines who work in the social justice and human rights ministries have been the target of red-baiting, or known as red-tagging. Government officials have accused religious institutions and faith-based groups of having ties to the New People's Army and the Communist Party of the Philippines (Saludes, 2021).

According to Mirage News (2023), Human Rights Watch reports that the Philippine government is using red-tagging and other violent tactics to intimidate indigenous leaders and activists opposing government-backed projects. For environmental activists and land defenders, the Philippines was one of the riskiest countries in Asia because of the intimidation and attacks directed towards indigenous peoples. Activists frequently face politically motivated accusations of defamation and other made-up crimes. Red-tagging Indigenous leaders and activists by Philippine officials has frequently resulted in fatalities and put their communities at danger.

During a Senate investigation into the practice of designating critics and dissenters as alleged communist-terrorists, Philippine government authorities red-tagged the Kalikasan People's Network for the Environment (Kalikasan PNE). Red-tagging has been known to result in life-threatening violations of human rights against citizens who are protesting injustices and abuses committed by the State. The Philippines new anti-terrorism law permits warrantless arrests of groups involved in alleged terrorist acts, exempting advocacies and humanitarian activities from terrorism definition, but red-tagging human rights and environmental defenders (Beltran, 2021).

Red-tagging has also been used to exempt indigenous tribes that disagree from the need for free, prior, and informed consent. The legal system has also been used to harass campaigners for indigenous rights, who have been the target of politically motivated prosecutions of terrorism, defamation, and ordinary offenses (Cabico, 2023).

Nonviolent workers rights advocates in the Philippines faced threats from radical organizations, including surveillance, arrest, and asset freezing under the Philippine Anti-Terrorism Law. The government and influential call center employers should condemn this red-tagging, as it could potentially endanger their lives (UNI, 2022).

Red-tagging judges undermine accountability and rule of law, while people continue to criticize government incompetence in health management despite restrictions on freedom of movement and press.

Red-tagging is a quick and lethal way to intimidate lawyers and other civil society activists who are speaking out against the overly securitized response to the pandemic and protecting its members from abuse and violence. Nevertheless, the public has been forced to see the abuse of power in a helpless manner (Deinla, 2021).

Fight against red-tagging

Berlineth Nymia Montes, a student leader and journalist from Naga City was also red-tagged by the military. They pressured her and her family, implying ties to terrorist groups. This harassment and red-tagging of student journalists by the Armed Forces of the Philippines is deeply concerning and an abuse of power. The International Federation of Journalists urges the Philippine government to stop intimidating student journalists and allow them to report freely (Media Centre, 2023).

When UN official Irene Khan, special rapporteur on freedom of expression and opinion visited Baguio City, local officials and civil society groups jointly raised concerns about red-tagging and its dangers. Their letter highlighted the issue's prevalence, stating that even city council members, like Vice Mayor Faustino Olowan of City Government of Baguio and nine councilors, had been targeted with false accusations and disinformation (De Vera, 2024).

Our constitutionally protected freedoms of association, the press, and expression are violated by malicious labelling committed by government officials, agencies, and their allies (NUJP, 2022). The persistent practice of red-tagging jeopardizes the safety of journalists and ought not to be tolerated. Irene Khan, the UN special rapporteur on freedom of expression and opinion, visited the Philippines from January 23 to February 2 on official business. She met with representatives of the government and civil society organizations to evaluate the state of affairs regarding the country's observance of free speech. This occurred after Khan and five other UN human rights experts wrote to the Philippine government requesting details regarding attacks and red-tagging of members of civil society, including journalists, in relation to the nation's anti-terrorism laws (Zabian, 2024). Communications Workers of America condemns Filipino workers' abuse under Duterte's regime, including red-tagging, and supports BIEN, a call center union. They urge companies to speak out against these injustices, as demonstrated by Zara Alvarez's murder (CWA, 2021).

Technical Literature

A case study is described as a thorough examination of a single unit with the purpose of comprehending a larger group of units (Gerring, 2004). It is also known as qualitative research that is defined by process-tracing and focuses on a single phenomenon (Baxter & Jack, 2008).

This study employs a case study design to provide a detailed exploration of the experiences of activists who have been labeled as members of the NPA (New People's Army) or terrorists. By focusing on three activists from South Cotabato, the study delved into their personal narratives, challenges, and coping strategies, offering a comprehensive understanding of the impact of red-tagging on individuals and their social environments. This approach aligns with Gerring's (2004) description of a case study as a thorough examination of a single unit to understand broader phenomena and Baxter and Jack's (2008) assertion that qualitative case studies are ideal for analyzing complex social issues like red-tagging. What makes this study particularly impactful is its focus on

the human experience. Red-tagging is not just a label; it is something that affects every aspect of an activist's life, from their safety and mental health to their relationships and ability to work. By listening to the voices of these activists, the study gave us a window into their courage and determination. It shows us not only their struggles but also their strategies for survival, reminding us that even in the face of great adversity, people can find ways to persist and push forward.

Single Holistic

The study adopts a single holistic approach, treating the experiences of the activists as one unified, global phenomenon rather than breaking their experiences into smaller, segmented parts. In a holistic design, as described by Depoy and Gitlin (2005), the focus is on understanding the entirety of a phenomenon as one complete unit of analysis. In this study, the phenomenon under investigation was the lived experience of being red-tagged as an activist, which is approached as a cohesive whole.

A single holistic approach works well for this study because the primary aim is to understand red-tagging as a systemic and overarching issue rather than isolating its components, such as psychological effects, social repercussions, or legal consequences. The researchers analyzed the activists' experiences not as fragmented sub-units but as an interconnected representation of how red-tagging operates in the Philippine sociopolitical context. By treating red-tagging as a single, global phenomenon, the study captured its broader implications for activism, human rights, and freedom of expression.

The decision to use a single holistic approach also aligns with the study's aim of understanding the activists' coping strategies within the context of red-tagging. Rather than examining coping strategies in isolation—such as psychological resilience versus community support—the study viewed these strategies as interconnected responses to the same phenomenon. This global perspective provides a deeper understanding of how red-tagged activists adapt, survive, and persist in their advocacy.

In simple terms, this holistic lens allows the researchers to capture the complexity and depth of red-tagging without reducing it to its individual components. Much like in the example of implementing an exercise program in a workplace, where the workplace is treated as a single unit of analysis, this study viewed the activists' experiences as part of a unified system. This approach is especially important because red-tagging is not just a personal issue but one deeply embedded in systemic political repression. By treating the activists' experiences as a single, unified case, the study emphasized the interconnectedness of their challenges and highlighted the pervasive nature of red-tagging as a sociopolitical phenomenon.

Research Questions

This study aimed to gain insights on the experience of being red-tagged activists of three South Cotabateños.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the experience of being red-tagged activists be described?
 2. What are the challenges encountered on being red-tagged activists of three South Cotabateños?
 3. What are their coping strategies in addressing the challenges encountered on being red-tagged activists?
-

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research utilized a single holistic case study to describe the experiences of three being red-tagged activists in South Cotabato. Three red-tagged activists were residents of South Cotabato. It allowed the researchers to focus on the lens of being red-tagged activists on one perspective and it gave a better approach in the formulation of the data provided by the participants' responses, considering that it focuses at one lens perspective of being red-tagged activists.

The researchers have conducted face-to-face in-depth interviews which is the most suitable and conducive method for collecting the necessary data. A face-to-face interview is a form of data collection in which the interviewer talks directly with the participant in line with the prepared questionnaire. This allowed for the collection of factual information, participants' assessments, attitudes, preferences, and other information gleaned from the participants' dialogue. In-depth interviews were conducted by the researchers in order for them to have detailed information about being red-tagged activists regarding their experience, challenges, and coping strategies. In the analysis of the data, the researchers have used thematic analysis to create themes that describe their experience on being red-tagged activists.

Setting

This study was conducted in different municipalities in South Cotabato. It is located in Southern Mindanao, the Province of South Cotabato. The researchers chose this setting of the study as there are a lot of organization forms here and professions that are very active in participating in issues that cause the people or environment to suffer. According to Human Rights Watch (2021), a human rights lawyer of environment and indigenous rights, Juan Macababbad, was shot to death last September 2021 by gunmen in South Cotabato in the Philippines. There are also activists fighting for the environment specifically on the open-pit mining issue in the province. According to Gomez et al. (2022), the Environmental activists are uncomfortable in Marcos' administration as they see that they are willing to compromise the environment for the development.

It is evident that the researchers chose South Cotabato since there are present organizations where activists exist and are highly probable to be red-tagged. The South Cotabato has the history of activism on issues like land rights and indigenous rights that can also contribute to understanding the national trend across regions which is red-tagging.

Participants

The researchers have gathered prospective study participants using the inclusion criteria they established. First, the participants who are from South Cotabato must be activists and are perceived members or connected to communist groups. Second, they must have received threats through the short message service (SMS), email, or even on their social media accounts. Third, the participants were professionals and students. Professionals and students are chosen in the study because in every organization where activists are present, professionals and students are existing and are also engaging in activities the organization implements, especially in fighting the nuances for their ideology against the government. Fifth, they are willing to engage in the study and have agreed to an interview. The participants of the study were three (3) being red-tagged activists living in South Cotabato and were willing to participate in an in-depth interview.

Environmental Activist is 29 years old, professional and residing in South Cotabato. The activist recounted being red-tagged after a company accused her of being an NPA member and recruiter in South Cotabato. The company, staffed with former military personnel, reported her to the AFP, but the AFP dismissed the claim. However, she remains under surveillance by the National Intelligence Coordinating Agency (NICA), which monitors her movements, creating a constant sense of fear and anxiety. Being red-tagged is both traumatic and life-threatening, especially as the Philippines is one of the most dangerous countries for environmental activists. She shared that red-tagging not only isolates her but also leads to threats and monitoring, making her prioritize safety over normal social interactions. She now avoids unnecessary outings, limits social media activity, and implements various security measures, such as installing CCTV and planning movements strategically. Despite the dangers, she continues her activism, working within a network of non-governmental organizations, civil society organizations, and like-minded individuals advocating for environmental and labor rights.

Social Justice Activist is 22 years old, professional, and residing in South Cotabato. Based on his responses, the activist described his experience with red-tagging as both alarming and challenging, especially during the early stages of his activism. Despite being a student at the time, he was openly labeled as an NPA (New People's Army) member by his teachers and peers, which he initially found distressing. Over time, however, he reframed red-tagging as a form of validation, interpreting it as recognition of the impact of his activism.

The activist shared that being red-tagged exposed him to threats, surveillance, and mistrust. He received direct threats via text messages and calls, was subjected to smear campaigns on social media, and felt constant fear for his safety. These challenges forced

him to be cautious, avoid public spaces, and seek legal support when necessary. He also witnessed colleagues being abducted and noted how red-tagging creates a hostile environment even within families and academic institutions.

He described the psychological toll but emphasized that he did not see himself as marginalized or "othered" by the label. Instead, he used red-tagging as motivation to continue his advocacy, believing it signified that his efforts were making an impact. To cope, he balanced external strategies, such as reporting threats to trusted allies and legal entities, with internal resilience and confidence in his cause. He actively encountered misconceptions about activism by engaging with students and communities, teaching them critical thinking rather than direct activism, and demonstrating through his work the constructive and progressive nature of his efforts.

The activist described her experience of being red-tagged as deeply traumatic and isolating. She was labeled as an NPA member by her neighbors, even those who had once sought help from her family, and faced death threats via text and social media. These threats escalated to the point where individuals visited her home looking for her, forcing her to hide and rely on her father for protection. The experience was so overwhelming that it caused her to stop attending school and seek refuge in a rural area to escape the stress and threats.

She noted that red-tagging altered how people treated her. Former friends distanced themselves out of fear of being associated with her, while neighbors avoided her, treating her like an outcast. These experiences led her to feel marginalized and "othered," particularly during events where her presence was either ignored or barely acknowledged.

The constant fear and lack of safety significantly impacted her daily life. She became hyper-aware of her surroundings, paranoid about being abducted, and hesitant to leave her home. However, she eventually returned to the city and continued her activism with renewed resolve, despite the lingering challenges. To cope with the trauma and threats, she adopted several strategies. She detoxed from social media and avoided unnecessary interactions, prioritizing her mental health and security. She also stepped back temporarily from activism to regain her strength and perspective. Over time, she learned to navigate these challenges by carefully choosing her engagements, remaining vocal on social media, and continuing her advocacy work through drives, conferences, and organized activities.

She highlighted the difficulty of disproving negative stereotypes associated with being red-tagged but chose to counter these perceptions by demonstrating her commitment to community welfare and speaking up for what she believed was right. Her resilience grew over time, and she now views the struggles she faced as necessary for the cause she passionately fights for.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers have used an in-depth interview guide. The researchers have formulated a self-made interview guide based on our specific research problems. The instrument was subjected to extensive examination and thorough deliberation through constant consultation with the thesis adviser. After which, The interview guide questionnaire was also validated by the validators to ensure the adaptability and flexibility of the questions to provide the necessary data of the study. After the consultation and validation, the instrument was used by the researchers in their one-on-one and face-to-face interview with the participants of the study. A set of questions have been put together with the purpose to obtain necessary data and information to describe their experiences as being red-tagged activists in South Cotabato. It consists of the three major questions that helped the researchers to gather and generate data. The first set of questions of the interview guide pertains to what are their experiences; the second set of questions asks the challenges encountered by being red-tagged activists; and the third set of questions asks about their coping strategies in the challenges they faced.

During the pre-interview, the researchers have secured a consent to the participants before setting the interview. The researchers have their interview guide printed in a short bond paper and a voice recorder to keep on track on the responses of the participants.

Data Gathering Procedure

First, the researchers have ensured to have the letter of consent signed. The researchers had an interview dry run and generated an initial analysis to have a preliminary data about their experience on red-tagged activists and before the official interview, the researchers have asked permission from the dean of the College of Arts and Sciences of Notre Dame of Marbel University. After the researchers acquired the required signatories and consent, the researchers have gone to the whereabouts of the red-tagged activists.

The researchers have contacted the participants before proceeding to their whereabouts and introduced themselves to each participant during an interview. Then, the researchers have asked if the participants have acquired the inclusion criteria that has been set in the study. Next, the researchers have adhered to the necessary ethical standards during the conduct of the study and present the consent letter to the participants following the interview. Then, with the help of the interview guide, the researchers conducted one-on-one and in-depth interviews with the three red-tagged activists selected as the study's cases in order to collect the necessary data until the study was completed. Given that the study has a sensitive subject, despite the consent presented to the participants, the researchers have established trust with the participants due to a personal connection with them.

Throughout the discussion, the three red-tagged activists have described their experiences of being red-tagged, on what challenges they have encountered, and the

coping strategies they have done. All data and information have been gathered and collected using an audio-recorded file, which were carefully analyzed. The recordings have been deleted after the finalization of the study.

The environmental activist has acquired 19 minutes and 44 seconds of interview at 5 in the afternoon. The interview took place in the participant's home. The Social Justice activist has acquired 37 minutes and 28 seconds of interview at 1 in the afternoon. The interview took place at the participant's home. Lastly, the Student activist, the interview took 16 minutes and 33 seconds in their home at 1 in the afternoon.

Data Analysis

The interview data have been transcribed verbatim. The significant statements were identified. By transcribing the responses of the participants, the researchers have prepared an equipment in order for them to evidently state what the participants have answered; A pair of headphones, a laptop, and a phone. Then, researchers looked for a conducive place to transcribe the participants' responses. Moreover, researchers began to listen to the interview and carefully typewritten on the laptop each response, word for word. Furthermore, reviewing the transcription by playing the recording again while reading along with the transcript to ensure the validity of the typewritten responses of the participants.

After the researchers have obtained the typewritten answers of the participants, generic thematic analysis was utilized to understand the patterns of meanings from the data on the experiences of the red-tagged activists in South Cotabato. The researchers identified the significant statement of each participant to fully grasp the question provided and each significant statement of the participants formulates a meaning that the researchers have crafted. Next, after the researchers crafted the significant statements, concepts were assigned. The concepts in turn have been clustered and their common themes are drawn to answer the specific research problems then identified and clustered the concepts from their responses. The researchers then transition from a detailed analysis of formulated meaning and concepts to a more abstract interpretation by interpreting themes to clearly understand their experiences, challenges, and coping strategies.

Limitations of the Study

The subject of this study is limited only to the red-tagged activists residing in South Cotabato. The participants were selected through the inclusion criteria, and through the face-to-face in-depth interview. The researchers have gathered and recorded all necessary data. The researchers limited the number of participants to an environmental red-tagged activist, a social justice red-tagged activist, and a student red-tagged activist, they are the only main sources of data.

One of the limitations the researchers have seen is the constraint in the accessibility of data. Gathering detailed information on the activists' experiences may be limited.

Additional factor is the potential bias for participant selection. Activists who have been red-tagged may be hesitant to participate due to fear of reprisal or due to being preoccupied with ongoing activism or personal matters. Another is that the study is subject to the inherent limitations of research, including time constraints, budgetary restrictions, and the willingness of participants to openly share their experiences. These limitations were acknowledged and were addressed through triangulation of data sources and clear articulation of the specific experiences captured within the study and by ensuring that the data that have been gathered were treated strictly confidential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion of the study on how being red-tagged activists in South Cotabato experienced red-tagging, faced challenges and the coping strategies that have been made. The succeeding sections are organized based on the identified case of the study.

Interpersonal struggle

The activists who were red-tagged experienced interpersonal struggle. They felt psychological distress and emotional discomfort.

Psychological distress

Activists experienced psychological distress when they were red-tagged. They narrated the events that happened when they were labeled.

EA felt anxious when she knew that this private company sent her name to the AFP and she was monitored by the NICA.

It can be internalized on these following statements by the red-tagged activist;

“Under monitoring ako sang NICA (National Intelligence Coordinating Agency, Inc.) nga nag cause anxiety sa akon”

SJA shared that,

“Harap-harapan mismo nila ko gina red-tag”.

SJA described his experiences when he was red-tagged face-to-face by someone.

SA also shared that she was texted by someone and threatened her whenever they saw her. There were some people who chose to be violent and hurt her because of her perception of being an activist.

SA added that,

“Gi texan gid nga hambal patyon niya gid ko kung makita niya ko... may mga tao nga maging bayolente ba...lain gid ang perspective saimo”

Emotional discomfort

Activists described their experiences when they were red-tagged. They felt emotional discomfort because of what would happen to them, especially that there were people who threatened them.

EA described her experience when she was red-tagged; For her, she was scared because her face was on the office of AFP, and she was being monitored. She also felt trauma that someone would abduct her because she was an activist.

“Scary gid siya...so uh traumatic”.

SJA shared that,

“Gikulbaan ako... feeling ko may mag pundo kag pusilon ko”.

For SJA, he is anxious about his safety because anytime.

Personal decision

SA emphasized that she experienced being bashed by the people. It was traumatic for her because people threatened to kill her, and because of that experience, she decided to stop going to school.

SA added,

“May mga tao gid ga bash saakon... Grabe ka traumatic... naka stop gid ko skwela because of that”

Mistreatment

The activists who were red-tagged experienced mistreatment by the people. There were people who treated them badly because they were activists who were labeled as terrorists or bad people.

No changes

For EA, people treated her the same, like a normal person. She was a type of person who was careful to interact with. She only interacted with her family and close friends. This group of people whom she interacted with treated her the same.

EA shared that,

“Same lang man ang treat sakon...normal lang gyapon ang treatment nila sakon”

Mistreated

Activists experienced being mistreated because of people's misconception that they are terrorists.

SJA shared that,

“Ang mga tao nga wala gapanapak sakon, may mga tao nga daw nahadlok na sa akon, kay abi nila gabitbit ko armas”.

According to SJA's statement, those people are scared to approach him because they thought that he was a terrorist who brought firearms. This was also the reason why people are neglecting him.

SA also added that,

“Nag distansya kag nang red-tag tanda... I was a disease... makalayo sila saakon daw abi mo mahawaan gid sila sakon”.

SA described her experience that when she was red-tagged, she was like a disease to the people, because they were so distant, afraid of being infected.

Positive Approach

Activists coped red-tagged in a positive approach. They took precautions to protect themselves from people who tried to hurt them. They were marginalized by the people; that was why they excluded themselves from socializing. Being treated as equal despite being othered.

Precautions

EA used tools for security purposes. She was cautious in interacting with people.

EA said that,

“Nagkuha lang kami cctv...magkuha sang body camera para mag gawas ko may recording...hindi ko basta basta makipag istorya sa mga tao”

EA emphasized that she used tools for her safety, like CCTV and body cameras for recording purposes. She was very cautious in interacting and entertaining people.

SJA shared that,

“Hindi...hindi mo pag eh treat nga iba ka sa ginapagbato mo... wala ko gina treat ang self ko as others...never mo gd eh treat ang self mo nga marginalized ka dapat eh level mo ang self mo didto sa mga nag red- tagged sa imo”.

He believed that he did not treat himself as marginalized or “othered.” Even if people are secluded and distanced from him because of who he is, he still fights for what he thinks is right.

SA added that,

“Oo eh...maka isolate ka gid”

SA felt isolated because of people who labeled her as red-tagged.

No absolute safety

The challenges that the red-tagged activist faced led them to securing their safety and security.

Safety Precautions

EA prioritized her safety from people who tried to hurt her. She was very cautious with the people she interacted with; in fact, she did not have any trust in delivery drivers.

EA said that,

“Gina prioritize ko ang akon security... very cautious ako...wala ko trust sa mga ...driver”

Alienation

The challenges that the red-tagged activists encountered were being rejected by the people and even their close friends. The misconception about activism led to alienation where people neglected them.

Rejection

SJA emphasized the challenge he experienced when he asked a question, but his question was rejected. He was stopped to ask those questions because this person who has a high position in office told them that those questions are not permitted to be asked.

SJA shared,

“Oo...in fact tung nag lakat si Chel Diokno sa school, nagpamangkot gid ko sato pero gipa untat ko pamangkot, tapos nag hambal si --- nga, bakit pinapayagan ang mga ganyang question”

SA felt alienated when her close friends chose to cut her off from the group.

SA said,

“May mga friends ko nga nag cut-off saakon... di nila gusto madamay”

Reticence

Red-tagged activists used to be reticent because people did not want to understand what the intention of their work was and why they were doing these things. They are being restricted from speaking due to the label they receive. They chose to keep going despite the misconception.

Misconception

EA described her challenge in making people understand what they are doing. They just want people to understand what activism really is.

EA shared that,

“Ang tao abi, hindi na nila maintindihan...big misunderstanding...hindi na nila maintindihan ngaa ginahimo ko ang gina himo ko”.

SJA also added that,

“Waay ka dira ya labot, bahala ka dira, biskan ihambal mo pa na sa atubangan ko, wala ko da labot biskan mapatay ka pa, amo lang gid na mahambal ko...basta wala ko labot”

SJA described his feeling of being silent about the things that people say and think. He does not even care if people think badly of him, as long as he is doing his job.

Inner turmoil

The challenges of being red-tagged gave activists a feeling of inner turmoil. They experienced badly inside of themselves because of what people think about them.

Emotionally unease

According to SA, she was hurt because of what people think about her. It was traumatic on her part that people think negatively despite her good intention.

She said that,

“Sakit...traumatic lang gid siya”

Resilience in the Face of Adversity for the Sake of Security and Safety

EA described the challenges she experienced, that it was difficult for her because of the safety protocols that she needed to follow. She implemented it to secure the safety of her family.

EA shared that,

*“Budlay ang challenges kay may ginasunod
gd ko nga security protocols...nga kung tani,
hindi ko na tani himuon pero kay syempre ang
security ko kag sang family ko ang need iprioritize”*

Difficult

For SJA, the challenges he experienced were very challenging. He limited his actions because of the people that tried to hurt him.

SJA said that,

“Challenging sya...so ano siya challenging”

SA added that,

*“Difficult and challenging gid siya...lalo na activist
gid ko...mga kapitbahay grabe init saakon”.*

She experienced the challenges as very difficult because even if she was not doing anything, people were still mad at her because she was an activist.

Security and safety

Activism is a very risky job where you can face traitors and enemies. Being labeled or being red-tagged, it is a must to prioritize the safety and the welfare of the people that are close to you, specifically family and loved ones. Safety measures are important because they can help individuals when their lives are at risk.

The cost of ensuring safety

For EA, the resources she used in implementing her security protocols are very costly. She needed to do it to secure the safety of her family and herself.

EA said that,

*“Costly and challenging kay more on
security abi ang akon...I can make myself secure”.*

Be vigilant

Activists coped with the challenges they faced by reporting them to high offices or consulting with any Law professionals. They also detached themselves in using social media to avoid any chaos.

For SJA, during severe cases of threats, he immediately reported it to a high office.

SJA shared that,

“Gina pabay an ko lang na...you need to report it sa mga offices”

SA also added,

“Nag social detox...gahalong gid ko sa mga tao nga ma interact ko...nag stop gid ko school”.

SA detached herself in using social media because of the bashing she received. She was also very careful in choosing people she interacted with because there were people who threatened her. She was scared of going out, which led her to stop going to school.

Achievement and social interaction

Activists prioritized the good outcome of their advocacy so that people think that their intention is good. This is their proof that their job is not harmful to people, but it is the opposite. They are doing the advocacy to help people and to be the voice of those voiceless.

Achievement and socialization

EA shared with people that her job has a good outcome; in that way, people would understand what they are doing. Every time she did her advocacy, she interacted with people so that people think that they are not harmful and they are not the people whom they labeled as terrorists.

EA said,

“Output sang ginahimo ko...naga interact gid ako sa people”

Communicating to people

Red-tagged activists used to speak and communicate with people because it was their job to know the other people's concerns and issues that needed to be addressed. Despite all misconceptions about them, activists were prepared to explain their side and their intention. They believed that through communication they can share their stories and ideas about the path they take.

For SJA, he always listens to people and hears their reasons why they think that activists are terrorists. After listening to their side, he explains clearly that they do not belong to those terrorists.

SJA stated that,

*“Pag mayo mga assumption sa akon,
kung sin o ka as aktibista, gina explain ko
na tarong. Ginahambal ko nga mali ang gina
isip mo na amo na, pero syempre pamatian
mo man ang reason ngaa amu na pang isip nila”*

SA added that,

*“Ginapadayon ko ang pag upod sa mga
drives nga gina himo sa org namon kag mag
attend sa mga conference kag naga speak up,
pati social media ko, grabe ka vocal.”*

Despite the challenges that SA encountered, she continued doing her job in their organization. She is attending conferences where she speaks up about activism so that people will know that their intention is good. She uses her social media accounts to spread information about activism.

Character and conduct

Activists continued doing what they loved. It was their passion to help people, and despite the criticisms, discriminations, and threats they experienced.

Building trust through strategic plans

EA plans everything before doing something. She used to do planning to build up her reputation.

EA stated that,

*“Ginaplanuhan ko ang mga gianhimo ko,
gina planuhan ko ang pag disconstruction sa
akon although budlay very helpful man siya...
gina build up ko ang akon reputation”*

For SJA, he emphasized that, in order to correct the wrong notion that people think about him, he needs to speak up.

SJA shared that,

*“Para matanggal sa ila ang mali nga notion
about sa akon...kinahanglan mo nga ikaw mismo
ang mag wakal. Kung gasulat ka, let your work
explain kung sin o ka, daw amu lang na siya”.*

SA added,

“Tough pero necessary siya”

All the challenges that she faced made it very difficult for her on how to cope with it. She had her perception that was different from others, so it was really necessary to experience those challenges.

The propositions were supported by the data that have been collected from the participants. The first proposition discussed that red-tagging creates a sense of powerlessness of their ability to advocate for change in certain issues that have been raised according to their goals. Due to interpersonal struggle and mistreatment from being labeled as terrorists or communist makes them powerless and delegitimizes their activism. They have been accused or labeled as a member of New People’s Army and a recruiter of the same terrorist organization that caused them to receive surveillance and threats from companies and the government that red-tagged them. The second proposition discusses the challenges the red-tagged activists have encountered have supported the proposition. According to the participants of the study, they have experienced that their safety and protection is not absolute that resulted in red-tagging.

In addition to the challenges they encountered, they were being alienated due to the stigma they received that made them undergo inner turmoil because of the challenges and labels they get. Also, their safety and the protection to them is not absolute. That made them fear from their own life to be at stake that draws up their own coping strategies that is discussed in the third proposition. The data however did not absolutely support proposition three since the participants have their different coping mechanisms to the challenges that they experienced. Specifically, the social justice activist has asked the legal professional for help rather than in the government such as the police or military personnel due to fear that he might be caught rather than being protected. The participants are doing everything to strengthen their safety to avoid danger to their lives, the life of their family and people around them. They have been interacting with people and making sure that the result of their advocacy will turn out to be positive and resourceful, enabling them to enlighten the people that once perceived them as a communist or terrorist.

Figure 1. Formulated Conceptual Framework

This formulated framework depicts the interplay between the challenges faced by red-tagged activists and the coping mechanisms they adopt, leading to a deeper understanding of their overall experience that comes from the participants' responses. The arrow signifies the participants who were directly targeted by the label and directly experienced the phenomenon which is being red-tagged activists.

The white centered circle indicates the participants of this study that discusses the experience, challenges, and coping strategies for being red-tagged activists. This overarching experience that manifests in the red circle is characterized by interpersonal struggle where they have to experience anxiety and paranoia in dealing with the label they get from people. Mistreatment which they receive from people who avoid themselves in interacting from these red-tagged activists and positive approach despite the treatment they receive from other people and from the government. It is placed in the middle circle to show how these experiences they encounter are the source of their challenges and coping strategies. This made them experience the adversity or difficulty of being red-tagged activists. The framework encapsulates the relationship between systemic challenges and resilience, shedding light on how red-tagged activists navigate and endure their complex reality.

The challenges of being red-tagged activists are placed in the red circle that include no absolute safety since they have received threats from text messages, private messages, email and as well as the surveillance they endure. Reticence by having no concern of what other people say about them and being restricted and silenced by the label they received and alienation by experiencing being marginalized by the people around them due to their activism; and inner turmoil by the circumstances of paranoia, anxiety and fear for their own life and safety. These challenges are rooted in systemic oppression, where activists are deliberately alienated from their communities and placed in constant fear for their safety. The alienation they endure is both social and emotional, as their marginalized status often results in stigmatization and exclusion. Furthermore, the constant inner turmoil, either surveillance or online harassment, creates an environment of pervasive danger. This is compounded by no absolute safety, requiring activists to constantly assess their surroundings and adopt measures to safeguard themselves and their families. Moreover, compounded by reticence is having no concern at what other people say about them and being restricted to speak.

In response to these challenges, there are coping strategies employed by activists that are placed in the gray circle. These include security and safety, accomplishment and social interaction, and character and conduct, which helps them stay resilient and motivated despite the difficulties they face. These coping mechanisms showcase their adaptability and determination to pursue their cause, even in the face of oppression.

It has also been visible from the responses of the participants that they experienced red-tagging from the government, private company, and in their society that highly contributes to their overall experience as red-tagged activists. They are being targeted by these tripartites explaining why they are placed in the arrow of this framework.

Overall, the relationship of these experiences speaks about the red-tagged activists' challenges and coping strategies in which having no absolute safety, they have to secure

their safety in order for them to protect their well-being, family, and friends. Moreover, having reticence, they have to show the government, private company, and society the accomplishment they have in order to show the success of their purpose as an activist. Furthermore, being alienated by these tripartites, they have to oftenly have a social interaction to prove their objective as well. In addition, they had experienced inner turmoil and manifested it with good character and conduct to manifest their true intention of objectives and break the stigma that is being labeled to them. In conclusion, these are the interconnected relationships of each of their experiences, challenges, and coping strategies that will help enlighten the overall phenomenon.

Insights

The experiences of being a red-tagged activist tell deeply personal and painful stories of individuals who, despite the dangers, dedicate themselves to fighting for justice and equality. These are not just abstract challenges but real-life struggles that impact people who wake up every day with a desire to create meaningful change. Red-tagging is more than just a label—it is a tool used to silence their voices, to paint them as enemies for daring to stand up against unjust systems. For these activists, the fear of being silenced is not hypothetical. It is a lived reality that threatens their ability to speak, to act, and to live freely, which in turn erodes the very democratic principles they strive to uphold.

Beyond the public image of activism lies an unseen weight—one of constant emotional and mental distress. These individuals face relentless threats, surveillance, and harassment, creating an environment where fear is a daily companion. Many of them live with anxiety, sleepless nights, and the haunting thought of whether they are safe. The sacrifices they make—losing their peace, their privacy, and sometimes even their families—highlight the extraordinary courage it takes to stand firm. These experiences also show the urgent need for emotional and mental health support, as their resilience is not limitless.

Red-tagging does not just isolate activists from institutions or authorities—it often alienates them from the very communities they aim to serve. The stigma of being labeled as communist or terrorist leads to rejection and mistrust, even from friends, neighbors, or colleagues. Imagine standing up for the rights of the poor, only to be misunderstood or shunned by the people you are trying to help. This social exclusion is heartbreaking, yet it is a reality for many activists who continue their work in spite of the loneliness it brings.

In today's digital world, the attacks on red-tagged activists do not stop at physical spaces. Online harassment is a modern battleground where misinformation, threats, and public humiliation are used to discredit their work. Social media, a tool they once used to amplify their causes, becomes a weapon against them. These online assaults deepen the oppression they experience and highlight the urgent need for safe and regulated digital spaces where activists can engage without fear of attack.

The challenges of isolation, intimidation, and heightened security risks faced by red-tagged activists underscore the immense personal and social sacrifices involved in their

activism. These struggles reveal a broader narrative of oppression, resilience, and the urgent need for systemic reforms to protect human rights defenders and create safer spaces for dissent.

Isolation is a significant burden carried by red-tagged activists. Being labeled as a communist or a terrorist often leads to exclusion from social circles, professional networks, and even family connections. This social alienation can leave activists feeling unsupported, misunderstood, and alone in their struggles. The stigma attached makes it difficult for them to sustain relationships or gain allies, as many fear guilt by association. From this, we gain the insight that creating communities of solidarity and support is critical. Peer networks, advocacy organizations, and allies must step up to break this cycle of isolation, providing not just practical support but also emotional affirmation that these activists are not alone in their fight.

Facing intimidation and danger is another challenge that significantly impacts red-tagged activists. Threats, surveillance and online harassment are used as tools to silence dissent and instill fear. These acts of intimidation are not only directed at the activists themselves but also extend to their families, friends, and colleagues, amplifying the psychological burden. These experiences reveal how systems of power use fear as a weapon to maintain control and suppress dissenting voices. However, they also highlight the courage and resilience of activists who continue to advocate for the environment and social justice despite these risks. This calls for stronger legal protections and accountability mechanisms to deter these threats and ensure that those who commit such acts are held responsible.

Heightened security risks force activists to live in a constant state of vigilance. They must take extraordinary measures to protect themselves, such as avoiding public appearances, changing their routines, and limiting their interactions. While these precautions are necessary for survival, they also take a toll on their mental health and restrict their ability to fully engage with their activism. This reality underscores the importance of providing institutional and community-based safety nets for activists. Advocacy groups, legal organizations, and human rights bodies must prioritize creating protective frameworks that enable activists to work without constantly fearing for their lives.

The coping strategies that red-tagged activists adopt—taking safety precautions, maintaining discrete communication channels, and focusing on the positive outcomes of their advocacy. These actions highlight the daily struggles they face but also demonstrate their strength in navigating such a challenging and often dangerous environment, all while continuing their fight for justice.

Taking precautions for their safety is a powerful reflection of the harsh reality red-tagged activists live with. They are constantly under threat—whether through surveillance, harassment, or even the risk of violence. To protect themselves, many are forced to alter their routines, avoid public appearances, and live with a sense of fear that never fully goes away. These precautions are not just about personal safety—they are a

reminder of how activism can be criminalized, how standing up for what is right can put someone in a position where they must prioritize survival. Yet, this also points to a larger issue: the systemic structures that force activists into such defensive roles just to keep going. It shows the need for safer environments and stronger institutional protections for those who are fighting for positive change.

Maintaining discrete communication channels is another strategy that illustrates the cleverness and resourcefulness of red-tagged activists. They rely on secure ways to communicate—using encrypted platforms or trusted, hidden networks—to ensure their work continues without putting themselves and others at risk. These actions demonstrate their understanding of the importance of safety—not just for themselves, but for the people they work with. They are often navigating a complex digital world, where threats are not just physical but can also lurk in the digital spaces where they organize and connect. This insight highlights the need for activists to have the tools and resources to communicate safely and effectively, further emphasizing the importance of training and support in today's technology-driven activism.

Focusing on the positive outcomes of their advocacy is perhaps the most powerful coping strategy. When faced with such immense adversity, red-tagged activists often lean on the victories of their work to remind themselves of why they keep going. They focus on the real, tangible change they bring about—whether it is empowering marginalized communities, spreading awareness about crucial issues, or pushing for policy changes that can improve lives. These positive outcomes provide them with the strength to push through difficult times, offering a kind of emotional fuel that keeps them moving forward despite the obstacles. This mindset teaches us the importance of hope and purpose in sustaining long-term advocacy. It also shows us how essential it is to celebrate even small victories, because they build momentum and remind us of the larger impact we can have when we fight for what is right.

The experience of being red-tagged highlights a system that aims to suppress dissent and silence those who challenge it, yet it also serves as a powerful call to action. It underscores the need for solidarity with activists, the importance of speaking up for the silenced, and building a society that values critical voices. These activists, despite facing immense personal sacrifices, inspire us with their courage and strength. Their struggles reveal the broader issues of systemic oppression and the need for collective action to ensure activism is seen as a vital force for positive change. By supporting red-tagged activists and amplifying their voices, we move toward a future where disagreement should be understood, not punished, and where justice and equality are fought for with resilience and determination.

Moreover, we can see that the government has somehow neglected this kind of issue; according to Tehankee (2012), his work in *Clientelism and Party Politics in the Philippines* has discussed the possible relationship of the government to these private companies.

The researchers have seen Tehankee's discussion in his work that the Government as a whole has this interconnected relationship with different sectors in which one of them is the companies. This becomes the clientelistic cluster networks wherein the patron and the client have the responsibility to give resources and support to each other. In simple terms, the machine or the companies have been providing the clans which are in the government in exchange of something that may lead into destruction to the intent for the people. In the case of red-tagged activists, this answers why in some cases, the proposed bill of Franklin M. Drilon and Leila M. De Lima were not pursued – this was the Senate Bill 2121 “Act Defining and Penalizing Red-tagging.” This ground may or may not be the possible reason why the government has no aid for the red-tagged activists and why the trust of these people for the government are not established.

Implications

To lessen the prevalence of red-tagging, it is essential for the government to implement reforms that safeguard human rights, encourage open dialogue, and create a more inclusive environment for dissenting voices. It is essential to have establishment of clear legal protections for activists and individuals who are at risk of red-tagging. This includes strengthening laws that prevent discrimination, harassment, and violence against those labeled as communist or terrorist threats. By doing so, the government can create a safer space for individuals to express their views without the fear of being unjustly persecuted.

Another crucial step is the need for accountability and transparency in the actions of law enforcement and military agencies. There should be an independent body or oversight committee to investigate allegations of red-tagging, threats, and harassment by state forces. This will ensure that those responsible for unjust labeling are held accountable, and that any misuse of power is addressed. Transparency in how red-tagging is carried out can help prevent it from being used as a political tool to target activists and critics unfairly.

Additionally, promoting peaceful dialogue and allowing space for differing opinions can go a long way in reducing the hostile climate that enables red-tagging. The government should facilitate platforms for open conversations, where activists, civil society groups, and government representatives can engage in discussions without fear of retribution. This would not only ease tensions but also help create mutual understanding between the government and dissenting groups, which is essential for addressing underlying issues and building a more cooperative relationship.

And lastly, educating the public about the dangers of red-tagging and the importance of free speech and activism is essential. Public awareness campaigns can help dispel the stigma surrounding activism and provide people with a clearer understanding of the role that activism plays in a healthy democracy. These campaigns should focus on the positive impact of social movements, highlighting how they contribute to progress and social justice. By fostering a more informed and compassionate public, the government can reduce the fear and suspicion that often fuels red-tagging.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the research, the researchers have sought a consent letter signed by the dean of the College of Arts and Sciences of Notre Dame of Marbel University with the signatures of research professor, research adviser, and department head of Social Sciences.

The researchers have followed an interview protocol before conducting the interviews. Hence, an informed consent was being asked from each participant of the study. The consent form contained provisions pertaining to the rights of the participants to accept or refuse to be interviewed, the confidentiality conditions as protections of their right to privacy.

To ensure confidentiality of the sensitive information which may be divulged by the participants and to protect the identity, pseudonyms were used. The participants were informed about the research objectives, potential risks, and how their information was used. The written informed consent was obtained before proceeding. The participants were also advised to withdraw from the interview at any point if they thought answering the interview questions and disclosing their feelings may affect their emotional health status. Researchers were respectful of the participants' contributions and quotes, and results were reported truthfully and honestly.

Acknowledgments

The success of this research paper is deeply indebted to the individuals whose invaluable guidance and assistance made the completion of this project possible. Special appreciation is extended:

To Dr. Jun Y. Badie, the thesis adviser, for his unwavering support, valuable advice, confidence, patience, and trust. The researchers are profoundly grateful for his role as an outstanding mentor throughout the research study, and they could not have asked for a better adviser.

To the Research 2 Instructor, Dr. Marcela B. Octaviano, for her patience, support, remainders, and valuable critiques throughout the entire duration of the research study, which played a pivotal role in making this research endeavor a reality.

To the panelists, Mrs. Cecilie Sharon T. Porras, MAT, Mary Joy Alave, MSPsy, and Dr. Marcela B. Octaviano, for generously sharing their knowledge and expertise. The insightful suggestions and constructive comments provided by the panelists contributed significantly to the refinement of this study.

To the language and technical editor, Dr. Jun Y. Badie, for helping the researchers to ensure that the text is grammatically correct, free of spelling errors, and adheres to the conventions of academic writing. This enhances the credibility of the study and prevents misunderstandings that could arise from linguistic mistakes.

To the participants of the study, for their kindness, willingness, and taking the risk to partake in the research. May their insights, satisfaction, and troubles that they shared be heard especially by the government.

To the researchers' families, for their financial assistance, moral encouragement, and unwavering support throughout every step of the research journey. Their continuous support and guidance serve as a source of humility and grounding for the researchers. To the researchers' loved ones and friends for encouraging and helping to stay motivated amidst trial. Researchers are wholly grateful of their existence.

Above all else, all the glory and thanks to the Almighty. In Him, they found comfort amidst the struggles and trying times. The researchers are beyond thankful for Him.

REFERENCES

- Advoc. (2023). What is red-tagging and why it is dangerous in the Philippines? (2023, April 27). Global Voices. Retrieved from <https://globalvoices.org/2023/04/27/what-is-red-tagging-and-why-it-is-dangerous-in-the-philippines/>
- Amnesty International. (2021, June 1). Philippines: Stop “red-tagging”, investigate killings of activists - Amnesty International. Retrieved from <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/asa35/0587/2019/en/>
- Amnesty Philippines. (2023). Deadly practice of ‘red-tagging’ continues under Marcos administration-(2023, March 22). Amnesty Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.amnesty.org.ph/2023/03/deadly-practice-of-red-tagging-continuesunder-marcos-administration/>
- Aquino, C. (2023, November 23). Red-tagging and reclamation: Manila Bay activists freed! - Berkeley Political Review. Berkeley Political Review - UC Berkeley’s only nonpartisan, political, magazine. Retrieved from <https://bpr.studentorg.berkeley.edu/2023/11/23/red-tagging-and-reclamation-manila-bay-activists-freed/>
- Baxter, P., & Jack, S. (2008). Qualitative Case Study Methodology: Study Design and Implementation for Novice Researchers. *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), 544-559. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2008.1573>
- Beltran, M. (2020). In the Philippines, a label can take your life. Lowy Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/philippines-label-can-take-your-life>
- Beltran, B. (2021). Philippine environmental defenders in the crosshairs of red-taggers.
- Earth Journalism Network. Retrieved from <https://earthjournalism.net/stories/philippine-environmental-defenders-in-the-crosshairs-of-red-taggers#:~:text=In%20December%202020%2C%20environment%20group,judicial%20killings%20in%20recent%20months.>

- Becker, H.S. (1963). *Outsider. Study Smarter.*
- Bright, M. (2023, March 21). The dangers of ‘red tagging’; and other lessons from the Philippines. Index on Censorship. Retrieved from <https://www.indexoncensorship.org/2022/06/the-dangers-of-red-tagging-and-other-lessons-from-the-philippines/>
- Cabico, G. K. (2023, January 27). Red-tagging used to harass, threaten IPs opposed to gov’t-backed-projects-groups.Philstar.com. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/climate-andenvironment/2023/01/26/2240392/red-tagging-used-harass-threaten-ips-opposed-govt-backed-projects-groups>
- CIVICUS. (2023). Philippines: Activists face judicial harassment, abductions and being designated as terrorists - Civicus Monitor. (n.d.). Civicus Monitor. Retrieved from <https://monitor.civicus.org/explore/philippines-activists-face-judicial-harassment-abductions-and-being-designated-as-terrorists/>
- Conde, C. (2023, January 26). Philippines: Officials ‘Red-tagging’ Indigenous Leaders, Activists Threats, Attacks Put Indigenous Communities at Risk. Retrieved from Philippines: Officials ‘Red-Tagging’ Indigenous Leaders, Activists | Human Rights Watch
- Crispin, S., W. (2022). ‘Red-tagging’ of journalists looms over Philippine elections. Retrieved from <https://cpj.org/2022/05/red-tagging-of-journalists-looms-over-philippine-elections/>
- CWA. (2021). CWA strongly opposes “red-tagging” of labor activists in the Philippines. (2021, April 29). Communications Workers of America. Retrieved from <https://cwa-union.org/news/releases/cwa-strongly-opposes-red-tagging-of-labor-activists-in-philippines>
- Deinla, B. D. I. (2021, April 1). “Red-tagging” and the rule of law in the time of COVID-19 - Australian Institute of International Affairs. Australian Institute of International Affairs. Retrieved from <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/red-tagging-and-the-rule-of-law-in-the-time-of-covid-19/>
- Depoy, E., & Gitlin, L. (2005, January). Introduction to Research: Understanding and Applying Multiple Strategies. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304129153_Introduction_to_Research_Understanding_and_Applying_Multiple_Strategies
- De Vera, S. (2024, January 28). Baguio councilors, CSOs raise red-tagging concerns to UN expert. RAPPLER. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com/nation/luzon/baguio-city-council-raise-red-tagging-concerns-united-nations-expert-irene-khan/>
- Freedom House. (2023). Philippines. (n.d.). Freedom House. Retrieved from <https://freedomhouse.org/country/philippines/freedom-world/2023>
- Gavilan, J. (2021, May 4). From UN reports to congress: The many times ‘red-tagging’ was used. RAPPLER. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/iq/list-times-term-red-tagging-use-united-nations-legislators-philippines/>
- Gerring, J. (2004b). What Is a Case Study and What Is It Good for? *American Political Science Review*, 98(2), 341–354. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0003055404001182>

- Gomez, H., Zuasola, F., Rebolledo, R. (2022). Bullish miners seek local governments' Green Light Across Mindanao. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/bullish-miners-seek-local-governments-green-light-across-mindanao/>
- Kumar, R. (2023). The year-long fight of a Filipino news site against red-tagging and state censorship. Retrieved from <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/news/year-long-fight-filipino-news-site-against-red-tagging-and-state-censorship>
- Lorenzana, K. T. (2021). Acts of terror on Philippines Activism: Exploring the cultural nuances of Philippines national sovereignty. ScholarWorks. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.calstate.edu/concern/theses/w6634890v?locale=it>
- Lau, B. (2024, January 17) Philippines: 'Red-tagging' puts activists at risk. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/01/11/philippines-red-tagging-puts-activists-risk>
- Media Centre (2023). Philippines: Student journalists harassed and summoned by army IFJ. (2023, September 29). Retrieved from <https://www.ifj.org/media-centre/news/detail/article/philippines-student-journalists-harassed-and-summoned-by-army>
- Mirage News. (n.d.). Philippines: Indigenous leaders, activists targeted by officials. Retrieved from <https://www.miragenews.com/philippines-indigenous-leaders-activists-935472/>
- NUJP Secretary General victim of red-tagging / IFJ. (2022, October 24). Retrieved from <https://www.ifj.org/media-centre/news/detail/category/end-impunity-2022/article/philippines-nujp-secretary-general-victim-of-red-tagging>
- Olmi, I. (2021, May 1). "Red-tagging" government critics in the Philippines. Istituto Analisi Relazioni Internazionali. Retrieved from <https://iari.site/2021/05/02/red-tagging-government-critics-in-the-philippines/>
- Philippines: End deadly 'Red-Tagging' of activists (C. Conde, Interviewee). (2022, January 20). Human Rights Watch. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/01/17/philippines-end-deadly-red-tagging-activists>
- Pingel, J. (2014). Challenging red baiting. Retrieved from https://ipon-philippines.org/wpcontent/uploads/ObserverJournal/Observer_Vol.6_Nr.1_RedBaiting2.pdf
- Pio, T. (2024, May 8). SC: Red-Tagging threatens right to life, liberty, and security. Supreme Court of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://sc.judiciary.gov.ph/sc-red-tagging-threatens-right-to-life-liberty-and-security/>
- Human Rights Watch (2024, January 17) Philippines: 'Red-tagging' puts activists at risk. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/01/11/philippines-red-tagging-puts-activists-risk>
- Human Rights Watch (2023, January 27) Philippines: Officials 'Red-Tagging' Indigenous leaders, activists. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/01/26/philippines-officials-red-tagging-indigenous-leaders-activists>
- Human Rights Watch. (2022). World report 2022: Philippines. Retrieved from

- <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2022/country-chapters/philippines>
Red-Tagging in the Philippines - Information saves lives | Internews. (2023, June 6). Information Saves Lives | Internews. Retrieved from <https://internews.org/resource/red-tagging-in-the-philippines/>
- Remulla (2022). Remulla on red-tagging: If you can dish it out, you should be able to take it. (2022, October 12). GMA News Online. Retrieved from <https://www.gmanetwork.com/news/topstories/nation/847796/remulla-on-red-tagging-if-you-can-dish-it-out-you-should-be-able-to-take-it/story/>
- Saludes, M. (2021, June 1). Mission in peril: 'Red-tagging' the religious sector in the Philippines — Photojournalists' Center of the Philippines. Photojournalists' Center of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.pcp.ph/blog/mission-in-peril-red-tagging-the-religious-sector-in-the-philippines>
- Santisas, S. (2022, October 2). Editorial: Call out red-tagging. SunStar Publishing Inc. Retrieved from <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/cebu/opinion/editorial-call-out-red-tagging>
- Teehankee, J. C. (2012). The Philippines. In Palgrave Macmillan US eBooks (pp. 187–205). https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137277206_11
- Thongyoojaroen, T. (2023, April 10). Red-tagging in the Philippines: A license to kill. Human Rights Foundation. Retrieved from <https://hrf.org/red-tagging-in-the-philippines-a-license-to-kill/>
- UNI. (2022). UNI Global Union denounces red-tagging and attacks on BIEN in the Philippines. (2022, February 7). UNI Global Union. Retrieved from <https://uniglobalunion.org/news/uni-global-union-denounces-red-tagging-and-attacks-on-bien-in-the-philippines/>
- Zabian, C. (2024). Retrieved from <https://news.tv5.com.ph/local/read/red-tagging-press-group-slams-red-tagging-of-community-journalist-on-social-media>